

Nucleophilic Addition-Elimination Reactions of 4- and 6-Chloroindolin-2,3-diones with 6-Chloro-2-hydrazinobenzothiazole

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Manuscript received 12 December 1988, accepted 21 February 1989

4-Chloroindolin-2,3-dione (1a) and its 1-methyl analog (2a) undergo nucleophilic addition-elimination reaction with 6-chloro-2-hydrazinobenzothiazole to yield 4-chloro-3-(6'-chloro-2'-hydrazinobenzothiazolyl)-2-indolinone (3a) and 4-chloro-1-methyl-3-(6'-chloro-2'-hydrazinobenzothiazolyl)-2-indolinone (4a) respectively. Similarly, 6-chloroindolin-2,3-dione (1b) and its 1-methyl analog (2b) yielded 3b and 4b respectively. 3a and 3b on treatment with morpholine/piperidine and formaldehyde furnished the corresponding 1-morpholino/piperidinomethyl analogs (5a, b). The compounds have been characterised by ir, pmr and mass spectral data.

IN continuation of our work on addition-elimination reactions¹ of 4- and 6-chloroindolin-2,3-dione (1a, b), we report herein the nucleophilic addition-elimination reactions of 1a and 1b with 6-chloro-2-hydrazinobenzothiazole.

Scheme 1. Reagents: (i) $\text{Me}_2\text{SO}_4/\text{KOH-EtOH}$, (ii) 6-chloro-2-hydrazinobenzothiazole, (iii) morpholine/piperidine/ HCHO .

It has been observed that 6-chloro-2-amino-benzothiazole does not react with 1a or 1b owing to its low nucleophilicity, on account of the influence of electronegative nitrogen and sulphur atoms of thiazole ring. However, nucleophilic attack of 6-chloro-2-hydrazinobenzothiazole on 1a, b under-

went smoothly leading to 3a and 3b in excellent yield. 1a and 1b were treated with dimethyl sulphate and ethanolic KOH to get the corresponding 1-methyl analogs, which were again treated with 2-hydrazinobenzothiazole leading to 4a and 4b respectively. Further, Mannich condensation on 3a and 3b resulted in the formation of 1-morpholino/piperidinomethyl-4/6-chloro-3-(6'-chloro-2'-hydrazinobenzothiazolyl)-2-indolinones (5a and 5b) which provided additional evidence for the structures of 3a and 3b (Scheme 1). All the compounds have been characterised by elemental analysis and ir, pmr and mass spectral data.

Mass spectrum of 5a displayed an intense molecular ion at m/e 461/463. Loss of morpholino-methyl group (m/e 100) yielded prominent peak at m/e 361/363 with a typical chlorine isotopic profile from which peaks at m/e 333/335 and 298/300 were observed due to stepwise removal of CO and Cl radicals (Scheme 2).

Experimental

4-Chloro-3-(6'-chloro-2'-hydrazinobenzothiazolyl)-2-indolinone (3a): A mixture of 4-chloroisatin (1.81 g, 0.01 mol) and 6-chloro-2-hydrazinobenzothiazole (1.99 g, 0.01 mol) in methanol (15 ml) containing glacial acetic acid (1-2 drops) was refluxed on a water-bath for 3-4 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and the resulting solid was filtered and washed with methanol, (88%), m.p. $> 280^\circ$; ν_{max} 3 190 (NH), 1 705 (C=O), 1 615 (C=N) and 730 cm^{-1} (C-Cl).

6-Chloro-3-(6'-chloro-2'-hydrazinobenzothiazolyl)-2-indolinone (3b): It was prepared by the above method using 6-chloroisatin in place of 4-chloroisatin, (77%), m.p. $> 280^\circ$; ν_{max} 3 150 (NH), 1 715 (C=O), 1 620 (C=N) and 710 cm^{-1} (C-Cl).

4-Chloro-1-methyl-3-(6'-chloro-2'-hydrazonobenzothiazolyl)-2-indolinone (4a): A mixture of 4-chloro-1-methylindolin-2,3-dione (0.005 mol) was refluxed with 6-chloro-2-hydrazinobenzothiazole (0.005 mol) in methanol (10 ml) containing glacial acetic acid (1–2 drops) on a water-bath for 3–4 h. The yellow crystals separated on cooling, were filtered, washed with methanol and recrystallised from chloroform–petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°), (68%), m.p. > 280° (Found: C, 50.89; H, 2.51. Requires: C, 50.9; H, 2.65%); ν_{max} 3 200 (NH), 1 710 (C=O), 1 610 (C=N) and 765 cm^{-1} (C–Cl).

6-Chloro-1-methyl-3-(6'-chloro-2'-hydrazonobenzothiazolyl)-2-indolinone (4b): It was prepared by the above method using 6-chloro-1-methylindolin-2,3-dione and 6-chloro-2-hydrazinobenzothiazole, (63%), m.p. > 280° (Found: C, 50.78; H, 2.46.

Requires: C, 50.9; H, 2.65%); ν_{max} 3 150 (NH), 1 710 (C=O), 1 615 (C=N) and 690 cm^{-1} (C–Cl).

4-Chloro-1-morpholino/piperidinomethyl-3-(6'-chloro-2'-hydrazonobenzothiazolyl)-2-indolinone (5a): 4-Chloro-3-(6'-chloro-2'-hydrazonobenzothiazolyl)-2-indolinone (0.005 mol) was suspended in methanol 10 ml containing DMF 1–2 ml. The suspension was warmed on a water bath and then formalin (1–2 ml) and morpholine (1–2 ml) were added to it with vigorous stirring. Thereafter the whole mass was kept at room temperature overnight. The yellow crystalline mass separated, was washed with methanol, dried at room temperature and finally recrystallised from chloroform–petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°), (68%), m.p. 227–30° (Found: C, 52.01; H, 3.87. Requires: C, 51.94; H, 3.67%); δ 2.52 (4H, $\text{N}(\text{CH}_2)_2$), 3.60 (4H, $\text{O}(\text{CH}_2)_2$), 4.4 (2H, NCH_2N), 6.9–7.6 (7H, ArH and NH); m/e 461/463 (M^+), 361/363, 333/335, 298/300, 183/185, 100.

The same procedure was employed to synthesise piperidino analog (5a; $\text{X}=\text{CH}_2$), (71%), m.p. 217° (Found: C, 54.60; H, 3.88. Requires: C, 54.78; H, 4.13%).

6-Chloro-1-morpholino/piperidinomethyl-3-(6'-chloro-2'-hydrazonobenzothiazolyl)-2-indolinone (5b): It was prepared by the above method using 6-chloro-3-(6'-chloro-2'-hydrazonobenzothiazolyl)-2-indolinone ($\text{X}=\text{O}$), (70%), m.p. 195–97° (Found: C, 52.01; H, 3.71. Requires: C, 51.94; H, 3.67%); δ 2.55 (4H, $\text{N}(\text{CH}_2)_2$), 3.60 (4H, $\text{O}(\text{CH}_2)_2$), 4.33 (2H, NCH_2N), 6.92–7.56 (7H, ArH and NH); 5b ($\text{X}=\text{CH}_2$), (70%), m.p. 220–25° (Found: C, 54.90; H, 3.89. Requires: C, 54.78; H, 4.13%).

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Head of the Chemistry Department for facilities. Thanks are also due to Dr R. S. Kapil and Prof. S. P. Singh for analytical and spectral data.

Reference

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